
PRINCIPALS' APPLICATION OF ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE AS PREDICTORS OF TEACHERS' JOB COMMITMENT IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE

Prof. Patience Nndi Egboka, Dr. Israel Chijiuka Oparaji & Chidiebele Justina Ariwuzo

Department of Educational Management and Policy,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria

Abstract

The study determined principals' application of organizational justice as predictors of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study was guided by four research questions and four null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level. Correlational research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study comprised 7,027 teachers in 266 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The sample for this study consisted of 1,055 teachers drawn using proportionate stratified random sampling technique. Two set of questionnaires titled "Organizational Justice Scale (OJS)" and "Teachers' Job Commitment Scale (TJCS)" were used for data collection. The instruments were face validated by three experts. Cronbach alpha method was used for a test of internal consistencies of the instruments which yielded overall coefficient value of 0.80 for OJS and 0.80 for TJCS respectively. The instruments were administered by the researcher and five research assistants and 97% return rate was recorded. Multiple regression was used to answer research question 1 and test hypothesis 1, while simple regression to answer research questions 2-4 and test hypotheses 2-4. The findings of the study revealed among others that distributive justice and procedural justice are strong and significant predictors of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. It was also found that interactional justice is moderate and significant predictors of teachers' job commitment. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that Post Primary Schools Service Commission should establish schemes for annual seminar of principals to upgrade their skills on application of organizational justice to continue to enhance the job commitment of teachers.

Keywords: Organizational Justice, Distributive Justice, Procedural Justice, Interactional Justice, Teachers, Job Commitment

Introduction

The quest for improving education in this modern era is a concern to all nations because of the conviction that it is an instrument for empowering individuals through the acquisition of skills and knowledge for development of the society. It is also a tool for developing potentials and inculcation of right values in individuals to make them become useful members of the society. Kenni (2020) noted that all the levels of education are vital to human learning and academic prowess but very significant is the impact of secondary school education as it serves as the link between primary and tertiary education.

Secondary education occupies a crucial position in the education system. It serves as the intermediate between the primary and higher levels of education. According to Isiaka and Tihamiyu (2020), secondary school otherwise referred to as post-primary education is defined as the type of education that prepares students with the mindset of contributing their quota to societal development as well as preparing them for tertiary education. Secondary education enables students to acquire requisite knowledge, sound ideas and fundamental skills to further their education at higher level. Teachers could be dedicated and highly motivated to carry out the task of imparting skills and knowledge in schools where there is organizational justice.

Organizational justice is the fair treatment that staff receives in terms of allocation of resources and rewards, explanations for decisions and procedures in performing tasks. Ibrahim, Saputra, Ali, Dagang and Bakar (2019) defined organizational justice as the employees' perceptions regarding the fairness of the treatment they receive in the workplace. Staff who perceive fairness in treatment are likely to be happy, dedicated to their jobs and less likely to leave their organization. Organizational justice is multidimensional construct which is concerned with rewards, interpersonal relation, decision-making processes and discipline among others. Rivai, Reza and Lukito (2019) defined organizational justice as the degree of fairness and equity in the rights of the employees and their duties in the workplace. Organizational justice focuses on fairness in managerial behaviour in the workplace. Contextually, organizational justice is the teachers' perception of fairness in assigning duties, decision-making, rewarding and controlling staff in the school. Organizational justice has three basic dimensions such as distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice (Onyekwelu, Nwogwugwu and Anizoba, 2021; Salim, Muhamat, Ibrahim and Ismail, 2021). The three areas were investigated in the study.

Distributive justice is the fairness in reward the teachers receive for their contribution to the attainment of predetermined goals of the school. According to Orajaka (2021), distributive justice is all about the fairness of the reward being given to employees in exchange for their contribution to the organization's wellbeing or goals. Distributive justice is the perception of fairness in allocating resources at workplace. Resources in this sense include wages, gratuities, bonuses, promotions and awards. Other resources could be workloads, responsibilities, facilities and punishment. Dumbari, Oparanma and Baridam-Ngob (2019) opined that if people felt that their work assignments and rewards were fair, they would show more commitment to their work. On the other hand, Ibrahim, Saputra, Ali, Dagang and Bakar (2019) opined that if employees find that they are being given less pay and promotions than their work colleagues for the same amount and quality of input, those employees will judge their work outcomes as unfair. Fairness could be ensured by the principals in the procedures of rewards and other activities of secondary schools through procedural justice.

Procedural justice is concerned with fairness of the decision-making process in the school, Procedural justice is referred by Rehman, Batool, Din and Hashim (2021) as the

perceived fairness and the transparency in the decision making and means of allocating resources or resolving disputes. It is fairness in the means of appraising staff performance, assigning duties and rewarding them. Procedural justice has an important element which has to do with fairness in listening to staff ideas and views during decision making. When teachers are actively involved in the decision making process, it could induce their commitment in implementing the final decisions. Procedural justice is concerned with consistency, accuracy, ethicality and lack of biasness in work procedures (Leventhal cited in Tyokosu, Emakwu and Ejoha, 2020). Procedural justice is crucial in shaping interpersonal relationship which contributes to the positive perception of interactional justice.

Interactional justice is the degree to which teachers are respected and treated with kindness, dignity and politeness. Razak and Ali (2020) posited that interactional justice is a feeling of justice that arises in a staff as a result of the interpersonal treatment received from the management. Furthermore, Razak and Ali (2020) stressed that staff who get fair treatment from the management will show a positive attitude, high commitment and be more satisfied with his or her job. It depicts how teachers are treated with dignity, honesty and respect. When the principals are polite, truthful and respectful to teachers, they may reciprocate through being committed to their job. When they are provided information about wages, promotion and other organizational policies in a timely, truthful and fair manner by management, it spurs them towards going the extra mile for the school in turn increases their job commitment and organizational effectiveness (Okpu and Eke, 2020). It is being truthfulness to the member of the staff. The interactional justice foster timely dissemination of information and cordial interpersonal relationship with teachers which could bring about a more relaxing and pleasing school climate that fosters job commitment.

Job commitment is the identification, loyalty and dedication to duties in an organization. Odoh (2020) defined job commitment as the attachment, involvement retention and dedication of members of staff in their work or duties in order to achieve positive outcomes or good results. Job commitment is the devotion and the willingness to perform their duties. It is strong desire and attitude towards work in an organization. According to Iwuagwu, Nzeribe, Iwuagwu, Akuta and Akaeze (2021), job commitment is the loyalty of an employee to the organization. Furthermore, Iwuagwu et al (2021) noted that it is a process of expressing identity, desire to belong to and willingness to contribute to the achievement of the organizational goals. Job commitment is the high desire to act in the best interest of the organization. Operationally, job commitment is the affective, psychological attachment and dedication of teachers in the course of discharging their duties in schools.

The commitment of the teacher is the dedication to the values, projects and philosophy of the school and willingness to make sacrifices for its success. Committed teachers could utilize their time and energy in teaching their students, show care towards their learning needs, work harder to cover their scheme of work at the stipulated and employ varied approaches to teach the students. Elijah and Enaohwo (2021) asserted that teachers' job commitment can be measured based on their feeling of being part and parcel of the school, syllabus coverage in time, punctuality and regularity at work by coming to school on time and are present on all working days. Similar to this, Afolakemi and Adeyemi (2021) noted that teacher who is committed and loyal to his or her job will exhibit high levels of job satisfaction, organizational citizenship, punctuality, dedication to school work, making extra time for students after school hours, implementing diverse teaching methods in the classroom and improvising instructional materials when they are not available. In the same vein, Okotoni and Akinwale (2019) noted that teachers' job commitment in learning institutions could be assessed by devotion and willingness to spend time and energy for the school's

success and spending extra time in preparing for the class. Some teachers who display negative attitude to work could be said to be uncommitted to their job.

Some secondary school teachers in Anambra State seem not to be committed to their jobs. To buttress this, Ikediugwu and Obiora (2021) observed that some teachers exhibit undesirable behaviours such as absenteeism, lateness to school and truancy like engaging in other activities such as selling items in secondary schools in Anambra State. Some of these undesirable behaviours among teachers seem to be induced by organizational injustice of secondary schools in Anambra State. Abonyi (2020) observed that there are some teachers who handle few classes, while others often complain of teaching many classes and therefore could not prepare lesson notes for all of them in secondary schools in Anambra State. It is against this background that the study investigated principals' application of organizational justice as predictors of teachers' job commitment in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

The ideal situation of desirable work environment is equal treatment of staff with regard to distribution of reward, resources and involvement in decision-making to create favourable work atmosphere for improving their job commitment. Teachers require to be fairly treated by principals to create conducive atmosphere which induce them to exhibit desirable work attitude in secondary schools. However, the perpetual habit of work lateness, incomplete coverage of syllabus, redundancy at work and absenteeism among secondary school teachers in Anambra State has become so worrisome. One may ask why teachers' exhibit poor commitment to their duties in the State. The answer to the question may not be farfetched from unfair treatment at. It seems that there are unjust distribution of responsibilities, workload and rewards in secondary schools in Anambra State. There are cases of discrimination in decision making and assigning subjects in the state secondary schools.

The principals appear to sometimes assign tasks that are not within the job description of teachers and without commensurate rewards for successfully execution of the job. Some principals seem to make use of abusive words when interacting with teachers portraying unfavourable climate in secondary schools in the state. In the light of the above, the study investigated principals' application of organizational justice as predictors of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the principals' application of organizational justice as predictors of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to determine how:

1. Principals' application of organizational justice and school climate as predictors of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Principals' application of distributive justice predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. Principals' application of procedural justice predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
4. Principals' application of interactional justice predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. How does principals' application of organizational justice and school climate predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. How does principals' application of distributive justice predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
3. How does principals' application of procedural justice predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
4. How does principals' application of interactional justice predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. Principals' application of organizational justice and school climate are not significant predictors of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Principals' application of distributive justice is not a significant predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. Principals' application of procedural justice is not a significant predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
4. Principals' application of interactional justice is not a significant predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Methods

Correlation research design was adopted for this study. The study was carried out in Anambra State. The Anambra State Government and people have high admiration for western education but there are cases of unfair treatment which induce poor commitment of teachers to their job and this justify the choice of the area of the study. The population of the study comprised 7,027 teachers in the 266 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The sample for this study consisted of 1,055 teachers drawn using proportionate stratified random sampling technique.

Two set of questionnaires titled "Organizational Justice Scale (OJS)" and "Teachers' Job Commitment Scale (TJCS)" were used for data collection. The instruments were developed by the researcher based on insight gained from reviewed literature and information gathered from consultation with experts. The first instrument titled OJS contained 30 items arranged in three Clusters A, B and C with 9, 13 and 8 items on distributive, procedural and interactional justice respectively. On the other hand, the second instrument titled TJCS contained 25 items which measured the job commitment of teachers. The three sets of questionnaire were structured on a four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree.

The instruments were subjected to face validation by three experts, two in the Department of Educational Management and Policy, and one in Measurement and Evaluation in the Department of Educational Foundations, all in the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Their suggestions were used to produce the final version of the instrument. The reliability of the instruments was established using Cronbach alpha which yielded reliability coefficient values of 0.78, 0.82, and 0.81 for Clusters A to C of OJS with overall coefficient value of 0.80. On the other hand, reliability coefficient value of 0.80 for TJCS which indicates that the instruments are reliable.

Direct method of data administration was utilized by the researcher together with five research assistants who are secondary school teachers in Anambra State. A total of 1,055 copies of instruments were distributed and 1,012 copies of questionnaires were properly filled

and successfully retrieved, indicating 96 percent return rate. At the end of the exercise, dully completed and retrieved copies of the instruments were used for data analysis. Data collected were analyzed using multiple regression to answer research question 1 and test hypothesis 1, simple regression to answer research questions 2-7 and test hypotheses 2-7. For the research questions, the coefficient r and the size of the relationship was interpreted using the correlation coefficient by Schober, Boer and Schwarte (2018), as follows

Coefficient	Relationship
.00- .10	Negligible correlation
.11- .39	Weak correlation
.40- .69	Moderate correlation
.70- .89	Strong correlation
.90- .1.00	Very strong correlation
.80-1.00	High

For decision on the hypotheses, where p -value is equal to or less than level of significant value of 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected but where p -value is greater than level of significant value of 0.05, the null hypotheses was not rejected.

Result

Research Question 1: How does principals' application of organizational justice and school climate predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: The Summary of Multiple Regression on Principals' Application of Organizational Justice and School Climate as Predictors of Teachers' Job Commitment

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Remarks
1	.873	.763	.761	.26859	Strong

Table 1 indicated that the correlation coefficient of multiple regression analysis between principals' application of organizational justice and school climate as predictors of teachers' job commitment is 0.873 with a coefficient of determination of 0.763. This shows that 76.3 % variation in teachers' job commitment can be attributed to principals' application of organizational justice and school climate. The regression coefficient r of 0.873 indicated that principals' application of organizational justice and school climate are strong predictors of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis One: Principals' application of organizational justice and school climate are not significant predictors of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 2: The Summary of Multiple Regression Analysis on Principals' Application of Organizational Justice and School Climate as Significant Predictors of Teachers' Job Commitment

Predictor	R	R^2	F	P -value	Remark
Organizational Justice and School Climate	.873	.763	538.221	.000	*S

*Significant

As shown in Table 2, the multiple regression coefficient (R) is 0.873, while the R^2 is 0.763 showing that principals' application of organizational justice and school climate can contribute to 76.5% change in teachers' job commitment. The $F(1/1,012) = 538.221$ and the p -value of .000 is less than 0.05. Therefore, since the p -value is less than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, principals' application of organizational justice and school climate are jointly significant predictors of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 2: How does principals' application of distributive justice predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 3: The Summary of Simple Regression on Principals' Application of Distributive Justice as Predictor of Teachers' Job Commitment

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Remarks
Distributive Justice	.724	.525	.524	.37910	Strong

Result in Table 3 revealed that the correlation coefficient of simple regression analysis between principals' application of distributive justice and teachers' job commitment is 0.724 with a coefficient of determination of 0.525. This shows that 52.5% changes in teachers' job commitment could be explained by principals' application of distributive justice. The regression coefficient r of 0.724 indicates that principals' application of distributive justice is a strong predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Two: Principals' application of distributive justice is not significant predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: The Summary of Simple Regression Analysis on Principals' Application of Distributive Justice as Significant Predictor of Teachers' Job Commitment

Predictor	R	R^2	F	P -value	Remark
Distributive Justice	.724	.525	1115.508	.000	*S

*Significant

As shown in Table 4, the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.724, while the R^2 is 0.525 showing that principals' application of distributive justice can account for 52.5% variation in teachers' job commitment. The $F(1/1,012) = 1115.508$ and the p -value of .000 is less than 0.05. Therefore, since the p -value is less than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, principals' application of distributive justice is a significant predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 3: How does principals' application of procedural justice predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 5: The Summary of Simple Regression on Principals' Application of Procedural Justice as Predictor of Teachers' Job Commitment

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Remarks
Procedural Justice	.852	.725	.725	.28824	Strong

Data presented in Table 5 indicates that the correlation coefficient of simple regression analysis between principals' application of procedural justice and teachers' job commitment is 0.852 with a coefficient of determination of 0.725. This shows that 72.5% discrepancy in teachers' job commitment can be ascribed to principals' application of procedural justice. The regression coefficient r of 0.852 indicates that principals' application of procedural justice is a strong predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Three: Principals' application of procedural justice is not significant predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 6: The Summary of Simple Regression Analysis on Principals' Application of Procedural Justice as Significant Predictor of Teachers' Job Commitment

Predictor	R	R ²	F	P-value	Remark
Procedural Justice	.852	.725	2666.805	.000	*S

*Significant

As shown in Table 6, the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.852, while the R² is 0.725 showing that principals' application of procedural justice can bring about 72.5% modification in teachers' job commitment. The $F(1/1,012) = 2666.805$ and the p -value of .000 is less than 0.05. Therefore, since the p -value is less than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, principals' application of procedural justice is a significant predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 4: How does principals' application of interactional justice predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 7: The Summary of Simple Regression on Principals' Application of Interactional Justice as Predictor of Teachers' Job Commitment

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Remarks
Interactional Justice	.561	.315	.314	.45533	Moderate

Result of data analysis presented in Table 7 indicates that the correlation coefficient of simple regression analysis between principals' application of interactive justice and teachers' job commitment is 0.561 with a coefficient of determination of 0.315. This shows that 31.5% alteration in teachers' job commitment can be attributed to principals' application of interactional justice. The regression coefficient r of 0.561 indicates that principals' application of interactional justice is a moderate predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Four: Principals' application of interactional justice is not significant predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 8: The Summary of Simple Regression Analysis on Principals' Application of Interactional Justice as Significant Predictor of Teachers' Job Commitment

Predictor	R	R ²	F	P-value	Remark
Interactional Justice	.561	.315	463.388	.000	*S

*Significant

As shown in Table 8, the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.561, while the R² is 0.315 showing that principals' application of interactional justice can contribute to 31.5% transformation in teachers' job commitment. The $F(1/1,012) = 463.388$ and the p -value of .000 is less than 0.05. Therefore, since the p -value is less than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, principals' application of interactional justice is a significant predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study indicated that principals' application of organizational justice are strong predictors of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This is in accordance with the finding of Sumarya, Kusuma and Suardhika (2021) which showed that organizational justice had strong relationship with job commitment of employees. The agreement with the finding could be attributed to the fact that organizational justice determines work experience and behavioural expectation which is associated with job commitment of staff in the workplace. Principals' application of organizational justice shape the nature of interaction, guidance and support received by teachers which could explain the strong predictors of their job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This finding is probably due to the fact that principals' application of organizational justice enables teachers to be fairly rewarded, respected and provided with required resources which could motivate them to display strong job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Principals' application of organizational justice is significant predictors of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This is in agreement with the finding of Sumarya, Kusuma and Suardhika (2021) which showed that organizational justice had significant relationship with job commitment of employees. This agreement is possibly due to the fact that staff in every organization requires fair treatment to induce desirable work behaviour. Principals' application of organizational justice influences the mood, belief and expectations of teachers which might be connected with the significant predictors of their job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

The result of the study showed that principals' application of distributive justice is a strong predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This upheld the finding of Aduba (2023) which showed that distributive justice was a strong predictor of job commitment of employees. The similarity in time span of just a year difference might not bring about disagreement in findings. This is contrary to the finding of Lawal (2022) who discovered that distributed justice had low negative relationship with the teachers' job commitment in public primary schools. The difference in geographical location and participants of the study with diverse work experience could be responsible for the disagreement between the findings. The possible reason for this finding is that distributive

justice ensures fairness in reward and workload of teachers which could motivate them and strongly enhance their job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The pleasant feelings developed by teachers for justly appreciated for achieving desirable results could contribute to the strong predictor of their job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Principals' application of distributive justice is a significant predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This concurred with the finding of Gichira and Were (2016) which showed that distributive justice had significant relationship with job commitment of employees. This also affirmed the finding of Dumbari, Oparanma and Baridam-Ngob (2019) which revealed that there was a significant relationship between distributive justice and job commitment of employees. The possible explanation for the strong prediction of job commitment by principals' application of distributive justice could be the happiness and satisfaction felt by teachers who are fairly motivated.

It was showed that principals' application of procedural justice is a strong predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This is in line with the finding of Emmanuel and Wosu (2021) which showed there was a strong positive relationship between procedural justice and employee commitment. This is opposing to the finding of Lawal (2022) who reported that distributed justice had low negative relationship with the teachers' job commitment in public primary schools. The disagreement with the findings might be linked to the fact that studies were conducted in different levels of education with participants who possess different qualifications and work experience. The possible explanation for this finding is that procedural justice builds trust and social harmony which could strongly contributes to strong predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Principals' application of procedural justice encourages teachers' participation in decision which gives them a sense of belonging and motivation needed to demonstrate strong job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Principals' application of procedural justice is a significant predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This upheld the finding of Emmanuel and Wosu (2021) which revealed there was a significant relationship between procedural justice and employee commitment. This also affirmed the report of Raza, Rana, Qadir and Rana (2013) which indicated that procedural justice had significant relationship with organizational commitment. Principals probably apply procedural justice to build trust and create favourable atmosphere that could account for significant predictor of job commitment of teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

The result of the study indicated that principals' application of interactional justice is a moderate predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This contradicted the report of Tafamel and Akrawah (2019) which showed that interactive justice had a weak positive relationship with employee commitment of university. The dissimilarity in time span and geographical location could be responsible for the disagreement with the findings. Principals' application of interactional justice enhance respect in relationship that exist between members of staff which create harmonious workplace that could be responsible for moderate predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Communication and exchange of ideas which is encouraged by principals through interactional justice might also account for the moderate predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Principals' application of interactional justice is a significant predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This supported the finding of Edeh and Ugwu (2019) which discovered that interactional justice had significant relationship with job commitment of teachers in private secondary schools. This also affirmed the finding of Kamile (2016) which indicated that there was significant relationship between interactional justice and job commitment of teachers in secondary schools. The agreement between the findings could be linked to similarity in level of education and participants of the studies. This is in disagreement with the discovery of Tafamel and Akrawah (2019) which revealed that interactional justice had insignificant relationship with employee commitment of university. The disagreement between the findings could be connected to the different levels of educations and participants of the studies. The role clarity and direction provided by principals to members of staff through interactional justice might perhaps account for the significant predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that principals' application of organizational justice are positive and significant predictors of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Principals' application of organizational justice enhance fair treatment of staff an that make teachers feel valued, comfortable, motivated to exhibit high job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Equality in handling teachers with their colleagues in the same level through distributive, procedure and interaction justice a can make them develop a sense of belongings and positive feelings towards the workplace which they could reciprocate with greater job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Post Primary Schools Service Commission should establish schemes for annual seminar of principals to upgrade their skills on application of organizational justice to continue to enhance the job commitment of teachers.
2. Principals should make more effort to improve the application of distributive justice by ensuring teachers at the same level are given equal reward, resources and workload to enhance their job commitment.
3. Principals should continue develop standard work handbook to guide the activities of teachers of the same level to facilitate procedural justice and enhance their commitment.
4. Ministry of Education should regularly sensitize principals on the value and ways to continuously facilitate the application of interactional justice to improve the job commitment of teachers.

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